

ECORESTO: ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION DATABASE USER GUIDE

by

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(version 2.1)

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ABSTRACT

In many terrestrial areas where humans depend on ecosystem services or where biodiversity is threatened, ecological restoration is necessary to address land degradation, control invasive species, and/or propagate the rarest threatened species. This kind of pragmatic conservation action has been one of the main preoccupations of modern ecologists and conservationists in Seychelles. A lot of work has been done and a lot of experience has been gathered. But the access to such key knowledge remains very limited and ultimately depends on interviewing or discussing directly with the actors, due to the scarcity of data collection and documentation. In addition, any knowledge based on undocumented evidence, and therefore relying entirely on individual memory and raw feelings or perceptions is likely to be biased, at least partly. Therefore, progress in the field of restoration ecology has to take support in new approaches for the factual documentation and data collection of all trials and errors, successes and failures.

To address the gap described above, we have reviewed the extensive conservation work done in the Seychelles through interviews with conservation champions and field workers, and through the reports and documentation available. We have also reviewed international literature related to ecological restoration databases.

After a few years of pragmatic work and conceptual thinking in the field of ecological restoration, we designed the first version of an ecological restoration database in 2016-2017, in partnership with Terrestrial Restoration Action Society of Seychelles (TRASS). This database continued to evolve and in 2019 we reviewed it completely and we started collecting data in the field using smartphones and Open Foris Collect. Finally, the most recent development was in 2022 with the use of R to elaborate further on the data compilation and its rendering to users in the form of an interactive webpage (shiny app). In early versions we were storing the data in a MS Access database, which did not allow multi-user edition. We have now shifted to using Open Foris Arena, which has its own smartphone mobile application and is still compatible with OF Collect Mobile for field data collection.

The data management system developed is not a sophisticated, technical product made by computer programmers or pure data scientists. It is a simple tool developed by field conservationists with limited coding skills. Therefore it has the advantage to be in line with the concrete needs of the field, to be based entirely on open source tools, and it is relatively simple to get familiar with, to improve or modify. It can be applied anywhere on the globe and include an export function to the Global Restore Project standards. This document explains all the steps needed to set up a copy of this database and how to use it.

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I SETTING UP YOUR DEVICES AND SOFTWARES

I.1 Installing softwares and the database on your computer

Originally (in version 1 of this database), we were using MS Access to manage data collected with Open Foris Collect Mobile on smartphones. The reason for using Access and not directly OF Collect is simply because OF Collect was not easy to set up and use (for us) for data edition, data querying, and backups. In July 2023, we shifted to Open Foris Arena (<https://www.openforis-arena.org/>), which is a simple, powerful and free cloud database system that works naturally with Open Foris Collect Mobile or even with its own Mobile app. Using this system, there is no setting needed and no server or software maintenance. In addition, there is no more need for MS Access and Open Foris Collect local installations. All that is needed is to request a free account to OF Arena, and to join the EcoResto database for Seychelles or use it as a template to have your own multiuser cloud system. Arena can still work offline for smartphone data collection, and it facilitates the use of the most up-to-date survey version for all users.

Get access to the Seychelles EcoResto database (e.g. for Seychellois partners)

- Request an invitation to EcoResto (bsenterre@gmail.com).
- Log in to **OF Arena** and that is it!

Or create your own EcoResto database using our template (e.g. for other users overseas)

- Create your free account on OF Arena.
- Download our EcoResto OF Arena survey design from Zenodo: https://1drv.ms/f/s!AIDJ_kfLf82sgaQPRVON9_MBNrC8XQ?e=aqkkC8
- Install the EcoResto survey template on your OF Arena account and use it or edit it to suit your needs (you will surely need to change the code lists for persons' names, species names and project names).

Optional settings and installations

- Install **R** and **RStudio** if you want to update the EcoResto dynamic webpage (shiny app).
- Install **QGIS** with the plugins 'QField' and 'Get WKT' if you want to use smartphone GPS navigation with a copy of the most important data, e.g. trees to be monitored, mother trees to collect propagules from, etc., and for creating WKT geometries for complex restoration areas. A QGIS project exist on Zenodo: see the link above.
- Install **Open Foris Collect** if you prefer to use OF Collect Mobile over the Arena Mobile application (not recommended).

I.2 Installing Apps on your Smartphone

You need an Android smartphone (some of the key apps we use are not available for iPhones). The most recommended kind of device for this use would compile the following parameters:

- Android 8 or more recent (for better GPS/GNSS¹).

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¹ Although we are very used to saying "GPS", it is now better to say GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) because there are now more than just the American satellite constellation (GPS), such as the Russian (GLONASS), the Chinese (Beidou) and the European (Galileo). In practice, we are so conditioned to the term GPS that it is often used as synonym to GNSS.

- GNSS, including GPS, GLONASS, Beidou and Galileo.
- GNSS using 'dual frequency' (see <https://barbeau.medium.com/crowdsourcing-gnss-capabilities-of-android-devices-d4228645cf25>).
- A micro-SD card slot (and/or a large internal memory, but better with a micro-SD card set as external memory).
- Not a too small model; you'll need a screen large enough (e.g. 15 x 7 cm).
- 6 GB RAM or more.
- Accelerometer, gyro, and compass.
- All-day battery (>4000-4500 mAh).
- Rugged (IP68-69).
- Wet finger tracking screen.
- Get also a rugged hard case for your phone and a phone bag.

Install the following apps (available from Playstore) after having installed your micro-SD card ('Allow' authorizations to these apps whenever asked during installation and/or at first launch):

- **Open Foris Collect Mobile AND/OR Open Foris Arena Mobile.**
- **GPSTest, GPS Locker, GPS Keeper Lite.**
- **SWMap.**
- **QField.**

Install the data collection survey from the EcoResto database

With Open Foris Arena, all you have to do is install the app Open Foris Arena Mobile and then load the 'ecoresto' survey to which you have been invited.

- In Arena Mobile, load the **ecoresto** survey directly from the cloud
- To check or install an update in the ecoresto survey on your device, when you launch Open Foris Arena, tap the icon to the top right corner (to see the list of surveys on your device), then tap “connect with server”, and you will see if an update is available.

If you are using OF Collect Mobile, you need to get the survey file from the Zenodo repository (see link in I.1) and install it yourself on your smartphone:

- Download the survey file "**eco_resto_v2.0_en_20230723T051147.collect-mobile**" on your smartphone.
- Open the app "Open Foris Collect Mobile".
- Tap the icon to the top-right corner and select the option survey.
- Load a new survey by selecting the survey file downloaded on your device.
- If an updated version of the survey is published, you will need to repeat the steps above. This will remove any data from your smartphone, so you need to make sure that you have already sent your last data to the database before doing the update.

II GEOGRAPHIC PLANNING AND NAVIGATION

Upscaling ecological restoration to achieve significant results requires being organized and methodical in a way similar to the spatial organization of traditional forestry work, i.e. working with clear maps and subdivisions of zones and unitary restoration areas. This means that the data management must include a Geographic Information System (GIS) AND that the field teams must be able to target their work to well-defined areas identifiable in the field. To achieve that, we use two Android apps: QField and SWMap.

Using QGIS and QField

Open the file /qgis/ecoresto.qgz (from the Zenodo repository: see link in I.1). If needed, look for a tutorial to get started with QGIS. But all you have to do is zoom in or zoom out, move the map to see other locations, and tick or untick layers listed to the left of the screen. If you are working with a different dataset than the TRASS example below, just create your own QGIS project.

To get the QGIS project on your smartphone:

- In QGIS, install the plugin QField/
- Compile your QGIS project to QField.
- Copy the QField compilation anywhere on your smartphone (better in the internal memory than on the SD card).
- Start the QField app on your smartphone.
- Open Project; open the QField project file exported from QGIS (e.g. ecoresto.qgs file).

And that's it! The QGIS database that you developed on your computer is visible on your smartphone, and if your location is ON, it appears on the screen so you can see where you are and where you need to go. QField allows you to easily visualize complex symbologies but you can also copy the layers and use them in your own preferred navigation app (e.g. SWMap).

Figure 1. View of a QGIS project showing the planification of zones to be restored and the overlay of plantings already done.

III START RECORDING RESTORATION ACTIONS

III.1 Basic principles and definitions

At the most fundamental level, all aspects of ecological restoration are based on three concepts:

- Types of restoration events ("record types").
- Levels of detail for the data collected.
- The notions of 'seedlots' and 'potlots' for the management of grouped observations.

Types of restoration 'Events'

EcoResto is designed to collect data on all kinds of activities involved in ecological restoration, from propagule collection to nursery stock management and georeferenced plantings and monitoring sessions done in the field, as well as clearing activities (Table 1). For users of eco_resto, it is essential to have a perfect understanding of these record types.

Table 1. Types of activities that can be recorded in the EcoResto smartphone app.

label_en	description_en
Propagules collection ('Seed')	Record seeds / wildlings / cuttings collection. To record the source location and dates for different species, and eventually to label the envelopes accordingly in the seedbank.
Seeds Bank Stock ('SeedBank')	Keep track of a seed bank's stock. Enter the tag_reference of a seedlot and update the count of seeds contained (or set to '0' when used entirely).
Sowing bed ('Sow')	Sowing collected seeds in the nursery's sowing bed.
Potlot creation ('Pot')	Creating new pots in the nursery, either by potting plants from the sowing bed, or by direct potting of wildlings, cuttings or seeds.
Nursery Monitoring ('NursMonitor')	Recording changes in location of pot lots (e.g. moved to hardening area). ALSO consolidating nursery stocks by entering not just an update in position within nursery but an update in the number of pots in a potlot.
Nursery dead ('NursDead')	Removing dead plants in the nursery. If you remove dead plants from a potlot (or any other import/export) on the same date as the recording of that potlot monitoring (or movement), you must count and record the number of pots in the potlot before recording the number dead pots (or any other import/export).
Nursery Import-Export ('NursImpExp')	Receiving/buying plants in the Nursery (e.g. from SNPA) OR Giving/Selling plants from the nursery OR getting plants out for planting OR bringing back to the nursery plants sent to the field and not used.
In situ Planting/Sowing ('Plant')	Planting individual plants in the field. This includes the direct in situ planting of wildlings, cuttings or seeds. For broad in situ sowing, use this category combined with the Basic level of details, in the next screen.
In situ Monitoring (of plantings) ('Monitor')	Monitoring planted plants in the field (survival, growth, etc.).
Soil-Humus collection ('Soil')	Top soil collection for use in the nursery.
Strip clearing ('Strip')	Opening strips along the contour lines in preparation for planting in post-fire thicket areas.
Clearing an area ('Clear')	Area cleaned/cleared for exotic species, or unwanted species, for example in the understorey in order to promote native plant regeneration or plantings.
Maintenance of clearings ('Maintenance')	Follow up work on cleared areas or strip clearing areas. Maintenance of strips.
Describe a Treatment ('Treatment')	To describe a treatment or type of action done to sites, seedlots, potlots or planted plants.
Other activity ('Other')	Use this category to record in detail any other activity, including time spent, complete team composition and contributions in terms of 'persons hours' effort.

Levels of 'Details' in the data recording

In the smartphone app, the most recommended level of details will be proposed automatically after picking a type of record for the restoration event (record_type).

Table 2. Definition of four levels of data collection details that can apply to all restoration actions.

label_en	description_en
Basic (group plantings, overall area, species/spp)	BULK IN SITU PLANTING OR SOWING. Pick this option for planting activities (field) where you do not want to record planting data for every individual plant, but rather for the total number of plantings done within a given area.
Basic (individuals, GPS, Species)	NO TAG, NO MONITORING. You can provide its own GPS coordinates for each entry, and for each species, but YOU CANNOT DEFINE TAGS (i.e. a unique code making reference to a specific entry) and therefore you cannot monitor growth and mortality of individual elements (planting, potlots, seedlots).
Standard (with growth measurements)	NO SOURCE TAG, NO TRACABILITY. Allows to record TAGS. Each planted tree will be observed with exact measurements. In the nursery, it can/should be applied to tagged potlots, and then measurements are given from the mean or modal value for all pots in the potlot.
Detailed (with full traceability)	Allow to record TAGS OF SOURCE MATERIAL. Therefore it will be possible to know, for a given planting in situ, the exact source of propagules used and the complete history of the planted tree since nursery propagation to in situ survival.

Define the elementary observations: pot vs. potlot, seed vs. seedlot

Ecological restoration demands upscaling and mass production in plant nurseries. Although it is vital to have a powerful system to monitor stock and productivity, we cannot individually monitor every seed and every potted plant. For this reason, the most typical unit of observation in the plant nursery is the 'potlot'.

A "potlot" is defined as any number of pots (potted plants, wildlings, cuttings or seeds) created together (same day, or nearly so), for a given species, with a given treatment (or no special or recorded treatment). The minimum is to define all pots of a given species in a given section of the nursery as one potlot. Nevertheless, it is important to be more detailed and to distinguish different potting events, which will then allow to calculate production time from potting to planting. Therefore a potlot is a group of potted plants (1) of the same species, (2) potted at the same time (same event) and located together in a specific area of the nursery.

Figure 2. Illustration of three "potlots" corresponding to three different germination trials done for *Medusagyne oppositifolia*. Each potlot is made of two rows of five individual pots. Monitoring is done by observing the modal state (i.e. most common or typical) for all pots of the potlot.

EcoResto database structure

The EcoResto database structure is very simple and is entirely contained in two hierarchical levels. The data entry flow is organized hierarchically in such a way to simplify the recording depending on values entered in dependent attributes. Besides the key attribute defining the "Record type" (type of action recorded), the attribute "detail" allows the user to select the level of detail wanted for the data entry (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Overview of the Open Foris Collect survey design showing the entities (tables) and their fields/attributes (columns).

III.2 Open Foris data collection

Based on the structure presented above, the user simply has to follow the steps indicated by the survey on the smartphone. You start by describing a "Recording event" which is defined as a given type of activity, with a given level of data entry detail, by a given team, on a given day (or time frame), within a given project and roughly in the same area. Once you have defined a recording event, you will record individual observations or actions done within that event (e.g. planted individuals). So the recording event has to be defined in a way that it applies to all the individual entries recorded within it.

- Create an **event** as a unique combination of record type, detail level, author and date.
- For that event, enter additional **participants** (if relevant).
- Document the event with **images** and eventually define the **treatments** being applied.
- Finally, enter the **individual records** for planting or potlots, etc.

III.2.1 AT THE BEGINNING OF ALL ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION ACTIONS

Each time you start a new data collection session that might require the use of the GPS, make sure that your GPS will be fast and accurate (smartphones are generally lazy):

- Activate the location of your smartphone (and shut down the wifi and Bluetooth, or even switch your phone to flight mode if you need to spare your battery). If battery life is not an issue, leave the mobile network on, as this will allow the smartphone to combine GPS with phone signals (A-GPS, or "assisted GPS").
- Start the app GPSTest and wait until you get a signal.
- Start the apps GPS Locker and/or GPS Keeper Lite and leave these apps running in the background until you finish your field work (to avoid the GPS going to sleep).
- Eventually, if you want to keep tracks of all your exploration paths, start GPS tracking with SWMap (see Annex 1 for an introduction on how use this app).

III.2.2 PROPAGULES COLLECTION

One of the first things to do for ecological restoration is to propagate species that are either threatened (for in situ conservation or reintroduction) or that are keystone for the ecosystem functioning (e.g. dominant or characteristic native species, pioneer species, etc.). To be able to report progress, it is important to keep track of the number of propagules collected, their types (seeds, cuttings, wildlings), and their exact origin (GPS). Later, we can then link the nursery production to propagule sources, so that we will know from which source material a potted plant in a nursery comes from.

- Open the Open Foris (OF) ecoresto survey and create a new event with record_type = 'Seed'.
- Pick the level of details 'standard' (i.e. the default value, to allow seedlot tags).
- Fill in all other fields of the event where appropriate.
- Enter individual records providing coordinates, source type, species name, number of seeds, etc. You can create one entry (one seedlot) per source individual (e.g. same tree) or per source population (same coordinates and habitat). If the seeds are hard to count, take note of the number of fruits in comments and calculate later the approximate number of seeds collected. If you collect seeds and cuttings for the same species during the same event, enter these in distinct individual records.
- Put the seedlot in one to several envelopes (depending on seed size and envelope size) and write the seedlot tag on each envelope exactly as provided by the app in the screen "Tag for the current observation".
- At the end of the day, clean the seedlots (remove dust, debris, and eventual pests) and store them until their use.
- Describe the treatment done to the seedlot in detail using the 'treatment' section (if the same treatment applies to all lots recorded during the restoration event). You can also describe different treatments separately, i.e. in a 'treatment' event (record_type="Treatment"), and then use the treatment unique IDs for data entry at the level of individual records. You can also use custom text in the event 'Description' or in the seedlot 'Comments' (depending on whether the treatment is the same for all seedlots of the event or not).

III.2.3 NURSERY PROPAGATION

There are two basic ways to start a propagation event (or trial) in the nursery: either by sowing in bulk in a 'sowing bed' or by putting propagules (seeds, cuttings or wildlings) directly in individual pots (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Illustration of the two main types of nursery propagation: left = sowing bed (to be transferred later to individual pots); right = direct potting of seeds. Direct potting is also used for cuttings and wildlings.

Figure 5. Methods for labelling potplots and sowing bed trials: left, permanent marker on the vertical side of the plastic pot; centre, engraved aluminium tag attached to a sowing bed area; right, recycled aluminium sheet written with permanent marker and folded to protect from the sun (here the tag is unfolded for the purpose of the illustration). The latter option is the best compromise in terms of cost, rapidity, and durability of the tag code.

The most recommended approach for data management in nursery trials is:

- Create a new event with `record_type = 'Sow'` or `'Pot'`.
- Pick the level of detail `'detailed'` (to create a seedlot tag and to record the source tag).
- Check all other relevant fields and define treatments if relevant (see III.2.1).
- Copy the tag code from the source material (e.g. written on the seedlot envelope) and record it in the `'tag_source'` field of the current potlot entry.
- Write the new tag code (created for the nursery potting or sowing bed trial) on a label clearly attached to the potlot or sowing bed area (Figure 4).

III.2.4 NURSERY MONITORING

Plant propagation always involves a number of failures. Therefore, recording all the potted plants is not enough. It is also necessary to record the number of potted plants that made it to a stage ready for use. Without a data recording system, the only way to know how many plants are currently available in a nursery is to simply go in and count, which has many disadvantages: it is slow, it is inefficient to account for different species and different stages, it is not transparent (for communication with stakeholders and partners), it does not provide explanations for stock increase or decrease, and it cannot deal with situations where a network of plant nurseries work together.

Therefore, the best approach to managing plant nursery stock is one that sees it as a shop inventory or bank account, i.e. where all credits and debits are recorded. EcoResto allows you to do that and also provides enough flexibility to account for data entry gaps.

There are basically 4 types of actions in nursery monitoring: potted plants can be purchased, sold, sent for planting in situ, or transferred from one nursery to another (`record_type = 'NursImpExp'`), failed pots can be removed (`'NursDead'`) and potlots can be monitored for their stage and location within the nursery (`'NursMonitor'`). In the case where plants are sent to the field and where the corresponding plantings will be done with the `'detailed'` level (providing tag code of source material), it is not mandatory to explicitly record the nursery `'export'`, and EcoResto will automatically interpret the in situ planting of a given number of plants from a given potlot as a nursery export.

- Use `record_type = 'NursImpExp'` for any received or given number of pots.
- Use `record_type = 'NursDead'` when removing dead pots from potlots.
- Use `record_type = 'NursMonitor'` to reset (update) the number of pots contained in a potlot of the nursery (as well as information on stage, health, size, photos, and position in the nursery, if needed).

III.2.5 SITE PREPARATION

Many types of actions can be considered for site preparation. In the Seychelles, it mostly involves the removal of invasive species. In EcoResto, you can directly record geographic areas where clearing has been done. You can also provide more details using the `'treatment'` component of the survey. This data entry is straightforward and also integrates restoration actions focussed on invasive species control at the site level.

- Use `record_type = 'Clear'` or `'Strip'` for any major clearing work.
- Use `record_type = 'Maintenance'` if the area is maintained with a much smaller effort or work force compared to the initial clearing.
- Include a description of any `'treatment'` details for any of the entries above.
- For describing a distinct type of site preparation, use `record_type = 'Other'` and use the treatment module to provide details.

- Use the module 'area' to define the area prepared simply by collecting a minimum of 3 coordinates (to draw a triangle), or walk around the periphery of the cleared area and collect a GPS point every 20m (try not to draw an '8' shape, but an actual polygon).
- If you want to draw more complex areas, or exact strips of cleared vegetation, collect these with SWMap and later copy or paste the corresponding WKT string in the field 'area_shapefile'. In QGIS, the plugin 'get WKT' can help you get the text string in WKT format that corresponds to a shapefile of any kind (points, lines, polygons, etc.).

III.2.6 IN SITU (RE-)INTRODUCTION (PLANTING AND DIRECT SOWING)

Restoration work in areas that have been degraded, invaded, or that have simply lost some of their biodiversity is tremendously important. In the long term (and even more rapidly), the rarest and most threatened species have a real probability of extinction, and local habitats can lose their originality and their resilience to disturbances. Reinforcing the native component in invaded ecosystems, by planting in situ a number of species that are propagated in plant nurseries, has been done for decades. Although local NGOs and governments generally know well the extensive work that has been done, it is generally not possible to present clear facts and maps. As a result, evaluating the success or failure, even just a few years later, is problematic and relies ultimately on the qualitative evaluation or impression of the actors having participated to the work (when they are still around). Simply being able to say how many trees were planted, how many survived and what their growth rate has been is therefore impossible.

In the 21st century, we can do better! Since around 2019, any smartphone can provide very precise coordinates and take georeferenced photographs. And database systems such as Open Foris Arena are now accessible to small teams without technical computing capacities. We suggest that planting a tree in situ represents such a huge amount of work (from seed collection to nursery growing, carrying to site and planting) that it is simply ridiculous to not take the exact coordinates of every planting done, accompanied by the most basic information on the species, actors and date (level of detail = "Basic-individual"). Beyond the aspect of the data itself, this is also the best way to acknowledge, formally, transparently and quantitatively, the efforts made by field conservation actors. In addition, if we have access to permanent aluminium tags, then (at least for the most precious species) it is really worth it to tag those plantings so as to allow the possibility of future monitoring (therefore using the level of details = 'Standard'). Finally, since we have to optimize our restoration work across the production chain, it would be a pity not to record, for each planting, the tag code of the source material (therefore using the level of details = 'Detailed').

The typical sequence of actions for 'Detailed' planting events are:

- Before taking any action, define the target area and ensure that it is ready for planting. Also evaluate the number of plantings needed and the suitable species.
- Make sure that the nursery plants are healthy and remove any other species, weeds or pests that may be on them or growing in the pot.
- Take the potted plants from the nursery and make sure to copy the potlot tag code on a temporary marking for each pot (e.g. use plastic tapes with permanent markers, as this code only needs to last for the day).
- Optional: Create a 'NursImpExp' event and record the pots taken to the field for each potlot (this can be skipped if you do plantings with the 'detailed' option).

- Carry the pots to the target site (it is crucial to give clear instructions to make sure that the pots are carried with the best care, considering the effort already invested into their production).
- Create a 'Plant' event with the resolution 'Detailed' (this can be done simultaneously by more than one person or team; in case the data recording is spread into different groups).
- Make sure that your smartphone has the location 'on' and that the following apps are running in the background: GPSTest, GPS Locker, GPS Keeper Lite.
- Collect one record for each planted plant within your planting event.
- Record the tag code for the source material (as written on the plant).
- Tag the planted individual with its new tag (created by the smartphone). For this, we need to use tags that will last several years in the rain and exposed to the light, so it has to be done on engraved aluminum tags. It is also important to pay attention to the correct and visible writing of the code, as it might need to be read several years later, by someone else.
- If necessary, record treatments done (see III.2.2 or III.2.8).

The case of an area being restored using direct sowing (or group planting):

- Same as above but select the level of detail 'Basic-group'.
- You will need to define the area being sown using the 'area' module.
- And evaluate the number of seeds sown.

Direct sowing of large seeds with extra care:

In that case, if you want to monitor individually the seeds sown and their germination success, you might need to follow exactly the same approach as described above for in situ plantings.

III.2.7 IN SITU MONITORING

Every 6 months (or month, couple of months, year, or couple of years), a few days of effort should be invested into monitoring all or some of the tagged plantings. To be able to do such monitoring, it is necessary to get the targeted planting as a layer in your smartphone navigation app (e.g. SWMap, or QField).

Typical sequence of actions for monitoring of in situ plantings:

- Filter out from the EcoResto database the plantings that you want to monitor and export their data with latitude, longitude, last measurement and tag code.
- Copy to your smartphone the exported data in Excel format as well as a shapefile (the Excel file might be useful in the field to search for tag codes for example when having difficulty reading a tag in the field).
- Add the shapefile to your SWMap project (OR update your QField project).
- Go to the field and use QField and/or SWMap to navigate to the plantings to be monitored.
- Start the Open Foris EcoResto survey and create an event using the record type "Monitor" and the level of detail "Standard".

- Record the tagged plants you see in the field successively and simultaneously check from the list if you are not missing any planting.

III.2.8 DEFINING TREATMENTS

Within classical ecological restoration work, treatments are typically being applied to sites, collected seeds, nursery pottings, and in situ plantings. And there is a huge diversity of treatments that can be defined. To deal with this information in our database, we have reviewed the few available standards that exist. The main one is the Global Restore Project (www.globalrestoreproject.com), i.e. "the world's first open-source database for restoration ecology". This database stores information on projects, sites, treatments, seeded or planted species, species lists, and monitoring data. We compiled all the treatment categories proposed in that database and added a few from our own experience. Then we grouped the treatment in broad categories (GRP does not deal with plant nursery preparatory work).

Treatments can therefore be defined as the combination of any number of treatment elements/factors and their quantities. For example, germination trials for *Medusagyne oppositifolia* included a treatment with 50% perlite + 50% peat, and a treatment with 50% river sand + 50% top soil. In that case, each treatment is defined by the combination of two factors.

There are three options for applying the treatment to particular data:

- Record a potting event (`record_type='Pot'`) and define directly the treatment in the 'treatment' module if it applies to all potlots of the potting event.
- If your potting event will include different potlots that have different treatments, then you have to first describe all treatments in a 'treatment description' event (`record_type='Treatment'`). Take notes of the treatment codes (unique IDs). Then record your potting event and enter the treatment codes directly for individual potlots.
- The third option is to describe treatments qualitatively in your own words by simply adding notes in the `event_notes` and/or `indiv_notes` attributes.

III.2.9 RECORDING EXTRA IMAGES OR PHOTO MONITORING

For the recording of pottings (potlots) and plantings, EcoResto only allows you to take one photo per potlot or planting. In some cases, when we want to document observations in more detail e.g. germination steps, or pest damages, it might be necessary to associate more images, including some taken by better cameras than smartphones. In such a situation, additional photos can be uploaded directly to the smartphone by copying the `indiv_id` code and pasting it into additional images loaded in the `event_image` module. For the use of external cameras, the additional images can be added later, from a computer, by logging in to the EcoResto database (on Arena) and editing the event containing the records for which we want to add images.

In the case of general photo monitoring, or if the user does not want to navigate to a specific event, the additional images can simply be added to a new event with `record_type = 'Other'`.

Typical procedure for rapid photo monitoring of a potlot using a smartphone:

- Create an event with the `record_type = 'Other'` and enter the observer name.
- Add the images directly in the `event_image` module and enter the tag code for the observed object (potlot or planting).

Taking extra photos with an external camera:

- Record your event and individual observations normally.
- Take your extra photos and note their file number as given by the camera (use the text attribute `indiv.photo_external`).
- Upload your data to the Arena cloud database, then connect to it and add the image files.

III.2.10 DATA ENTRY FOR PAST RESTORATION EVENTS AND THIRD PARTY DATA

EcoResto is a flexible system, that allows you to record third party information. For example, someone collected propagules for you but did not collect the data using EcoResto. You can take note of the details with that person and record the propagule collection data for him/her.

You can even record historical trials described in reports or publications. All you need to know is what species were planted, in what approximate number, by whom, and at what date, and you need to draw an approximate polygon representing the target area. Such data can easily be entered as a group planting event (details level = Basic-group).

IV UPLOADING NEW DATA TO THE DATABASE

Do not let the data accumulate on your smartphone! This would lead to a slower upload if you are using Open Foris Arena Mobile, or could fail if you use Open Foris Collect Mobile (heavy data collection sessions with more than 500Mb can fail to export).

Upload your data when using Open Foris Collect Mobile

- Export from OF Collect Mobile, DO NOT SELECT "exclude images", and SELECT the option to export to your device's internal memory (download folder).
- Connect your phone and copy the ".collect-data" file to your computer.
- Connect to OF Arena EcoResto cloud database.
- Data Import: from Collect format, select the ".collect-data" file and upload (if you do not have the required access rights, send your ".collect-data" file to a database manager (e.g. using WeTransfer)).
- After migrating your data from Open Foris Collect Mobile, delete all your EcoResto records from your smartphone.

Upload your data when using Open Foris Arena Mobile

- When you have an internet connection, simply 'connect to server' from your Arena app.
- After uploading your data, you can delete them from your local app on your smartphone (it will remain on the cloud database, where you can edit your records).

Note that if you edit your data on your smartphone after it has uploaded to the cloud database, the updates won't be transferred to the cloud database (unless the corresponding entries are first deleted from the cloud database). Therefore the best approach is to edit data that has been uploaded only to the cloud database.

Dealing with images

OF Arena is limited to 10Gb per user account. Therefore, images cannot be accumulated for several years on Arena, and it is recommendable to transfer them to our own BIO server. In addition, if we want to access the images using a shiny app, it is still necessary to make a copy of those images on our own server (BIO). To do that:

- Download the images from the OF Arena database.
- Copy the downloaded images to the server at the path location defined in the database.
- The path location should be <https://www.bio.gov.sc/image/Bio/ZForis/YEAR/>, where 'YEAR' is the year the photo was taken.
- For images taken with external cameras, the path should be <https://www.bio.gov.sc/image/Bio/OWNER/DEVICE/YEAR>, where OWNER is the owner of the device, DEVICE is a unique code identifying the camera and YEAR is the year that the photo was taken.

Note that, when shifting from MS Access to OF Arena, we had to migrate our data, but for the ca. 10Gb of images gathered since 2016 in EcoResto, it was not possible to upload them one by one. Therefore, the OF Arena EcoResto database is also used, more generally, to store the information on all these images stored outside of Arena.

V EDITING ECORESTO DATA

Shifting from MS Access to Open Foris Arena makes it easy to edit the data on the EcoResto database in a multi-user configuration. Simply connect to OF Arena from your computer, navigate through the records and edit when necessary.

We are only starting to use OF Arena, so we will provide more help later, when we know better how to use the various data cleaning functionalities.

VI VISUALIZING THE DATA AND RESULTS

Again, there is a lot to learn in terms of what can be done within OF Arena. But at this stage, what we have is an R script that is based on the EcoResto Arena database (as csv files). The R script can simply be rerun to update our Shiny app:

- Export data and lists (categories) from EcoResto Arena, as csv files (6 files).
- Run the Rmd script that compiles the data for the Shiny app (ecoresto_v2.1.Rmd).
- Run the R script that creates the Shiny app (see Zenodo: [app/ecoresto/app.R](https://zenodo.org/record/1488888)).
- Upload the changes to the shinyapps.io free server (Figure 6) (you need to create a free account at shinyapps.io).

The interactive webpage (shiny app: <https://bsenterre.shinyapps.io/ecoresto/>) provides access to key project statistics for all EcoResto contributors, users, partners, and other stakeholders.

- Tab-2: Search for any potlot or other data and find out details about it, including the event_id code for editing in the OF Arena cloud database.
- Tab-3: Get basic information and evaluate the progress of a project.
- Tab-4: View a map of the restoration work done, including propagule collections and nurseries.
- Tab-5: View main project data formatted to the Global Restore Project standards.

- Tab-6: View detailed nursery stock and potlots.
- Tab-7: View all nursery trial methods, and search using any treatment factor.
- Tab-8: View growth and survival from different nursery trials.
- Tab-9: View images stored in the database. You can search them based on tag codes and species names. To get specific tag codes that you might be interested in, use the other tabs to explore the database and find the tag you are interested in.

Figure 6. Overview of the shiny app providing the main statistics on propagule collection, nursery pots and stock, and in situ planting done per species.

Other elements that can be added (but we need more feedback from the users):

- Phenology data for collected propagules.
- Nursery stock per species (rows) and per month (columns).
- Clearing area per site and per year or month.
- Number of individuals planted in the field per species (rows) and per month (columns).

- Map of all plantings made in restoration sites, with a legend showing those tagged vs. not tagged (symbol shape), the corresponding project or treatment (colour) and the number of monitoring done (symbol size).
- Assessment of the efficiency of the different restoration steps (seed to pot, pot to field, etc.).
- Assessment of the survival and growth rates depending on various factors (time, species, treatment, environment, etc.).

VII WORKING WITH PROJECTS

In order to develop the export function for Global Restore Project (GRP), we have introduced in version 2.1 the possibility to describe formally projects. This is implemented very simply by adding the category 'Project' in the list of 'record_types'. As in GRP, a project can be related to one-to-many sites, but we have added a second element to record explicit indicators, which are generally defined in project documents and correspond to deliverables.

Naturally, we then added the possibility to record project evaluations, which are measured results for the defined indicators.

In the R script that compiles ecoresto data, we have not yet developed a fully interactive processing of projects, so at this point the compilation is done for the "Franklinia" project currently being implemented by PCA.

VIII CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The EcoResto database has been built based on the authors' experience in practical ecological restoration for over a decade. Although our technical computing or coding skills are limited, we managed to find a system that is completely manageable by conservation actors and that relies entirely on open source and free tools.

Conceptually, learning to use EcoResto depends largely on the correct understanding of only three aspects: the types of actions (`record_type`), the levels of detail, and the notion of potlots or seedlots. With a minimum of effort, it is possible to be trained in its use within a day of indoor explanations followed by field demonstration and some practice.

We hope that this can eventually help others who are looking for similar solutions in a context where we have limited IT resources available.

IX ANNEXES

Annex 1. Introduction on the use of SWMap

Annex 2. Organizing a nursery into zones, or a planting site into a visible positioning system with infra-metric resolution.

Annex 3. Developing in situ nurseries.

Annex 4. Developing a seed bank.